

THE PHENOMENON OF CONFORMISM AND ITS IMPACT ON PERSONAL PSYCHOLOGY

Saydaliyeva Mekhriniso

Teacher of the Department of Psychology of Termiz State University.

E-mail: saydaliyevamekhriniso@gmail.com

Phone number: (99) 542-91-43.

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the psychological foundations of the phenomenon of conformism, discusses how conformism, that is, the adaptation of an individual to the thoughts and behavior of social groups, affects the internal views and identity of the individual. It also discusses the role of conformism in human psychology, how it manifests itself in social and cultural contexts, as well as social pressure, its positive and negative sides, as well as strategies for preserving personal opinion and freedom.*

Keywords: *conformism, social influence, group pressure, internal and external conformity, motivation for approval, social identification, group dynamics.*

ФЕНОМЕН КОНФОРМИЗМА И ЕГО ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ПСИХОЛОГИЮ ЛИЧНОСТИ

Аннотация. *В статье анализируются психологические основы феномена конформизма, обсуждается, как конформизм, то есть приспособление личности к мыслям и поведению социальных групп, влияет на внутренние взгляды и идентичность личности.*

Также обсуждается роль конформизма в психологии человека, как он проявляется в социальных и культурных контекстах, а также социальное давление, его положительные и отрицательные стороны, а также стратегии сохранения личного мнения и свободы.

Ключевые слова: *конформизм, социальное влияние, групповое давление, внутренняя и внешняя конформность, мотивация одобрения, социальная идентификация, групповая динамика.*

Conformism is the process of an individual adapting their thoughts, feelings and behavior to the norms and rules of the group. Such behavior is manifested in many social situations and can affect a person's self-esteem, ability to think logically, and level of independence.

Conformism is the acceptance of the existing order of things under the influence of others without critical analysis and development of one's own position. However, a situation in which a person consciously forms his own opinion and then it is clear that this coincides with the opinion of the group is not a case of conformism.

Types of conformism:

1. External conformism - a manifestation of agreement, in which a person internally does not consider the opinion of the group to be correct;
2. Internal conformism - a change of opinion in favor of the group, when a person sincerely begins to consider it true.

To some extent, every person has a tendency to conform, especially in appearance. Researchers have also concluded that personal characteristics can affect the level of conformity.

For example, people with low self-esteem are more susceptible to group influence. And uncertainty about the correctness of one's own opinion contributes to increased conformity.

The experiments of the American psychologist Lawrence Kohlberg showed that people with high moral maturity are less prone to conformist behavior. They make decisions based on universal moral standards and principles of conscience, and do not submit to the opinion of a particular group or authoritative person.

The relationship between locus of control and conformity

Locus of control is a person's tendency to attribute responsibility and the results of their actions to themselves or to external circumstances. There are two types of locus of control:

1. Internal (internal) - explaining the reasons for their behavior by analyzing the situation and taking responsibility for the result. People with low levels of conformity are more likely to have this type of locus of control;
2. External (external) - explaining the reasons for their behavior under the influence of external factors and shifting responsibility for the result to the environment or external conditions.

People with a high level of conformity have an external locus of control. They are more obedient, driven by the desire to gain the approval of the group and avoid punishment. Some of them, at first glance, seem conscious and even take responsibility for their actions. But if you listen to their speech, everything falls into place. What distinguishes these people:

They often quote those whom they have chosen as authorities, instead of expressing their own judgments and analytical conclusions. They act within the framework of accepted laws and rules and try to teach others to do the same. Moreover, if something is not written or specified in the rules, they do not take it into account. They may engage in disruptive behavior toward others unless the rules state that they cannot.

Types of Conformity:

1. Social Conformity: This type is related to the individual's acceptance of ideas or behaviors that are accepted by others. For example, economic or political ideas, fashion, and other social norms;

2. Mental Conformity: This occurs as a result of the individual comparing their beliefs or opinions with those of others. In such cases, the individual may control others with their thoughts and be influenced by them.

The psychological basis of conformity depends on several factors:

1. Social Influence: In social psychology, there are concepts of "voluntary influence" (informational social influence) and "non-voluntary influence of society" (normative social influence). In the first type, individuals try to learn from the thoughts and behaviors of others, while in the second type, individuals are afraid of avoiding the group and attracting their attention;

2. Group pressure: Conformity to the opinions of others is often due to the opinions of the most powerful members of the group.

REFERENCES

1. Кондратьев М. Ю., Ильин В. А. Конформизм // Азбука социального психолога-практика. — Москва: Пер Сэ, 2007;
2. Андреева Г. М. Социальная психология: Учебник для высших учебных заведений. — 5-е изд., испр. и доп.. — М.: Аспект Пресс, 2008.
3. <https://skillbox.ru/media/growth/conformism/>
4. Muhiddinova, D., & Saydaliyeva, M. (2023). MANIFESTATION OF DESTRUCTIVE RELIGIOUS BEHAVIOR IN PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS. Modern Science and Research, 2(6), 934-938.
5. Saydaliyeva, M. (2023). PSYCHODIAGNOSTICS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AGRESSIVENESS AND RELIGION IN ADOLESCENTS (IN MUSLIM AND CHRISTIAN TEENAGERS). Modern Science and Research, 2(7), 802-808.
6. XUDOYQULOVA, S., & SAYDALIYEVA, M. (2023). The Role of Parental Psychology in the Formation of a Particular Religious Beliefs in A Child. Eurasian Scientific Herald, 21, 54-58.